

Green removal of DUV polarity modified PMMA for wet transfer of CVD graphene

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Quality of graphene after different PMMA removal procedures

To compare the method of PMMA removal described in the main text, we have prepared and characterized additional PMMA/Graphene samples using the same wet-transfer process (steps 1-3), but with PMMA removed with common solvents: acetone and chloroform. A total of 6 samples were prepared in two runs: three samples with DUV treatment and development in aqueous IPA

(samples DUV1- DUV3) and two samples for PMMA removal for 18 hours at 23°C in chloroform and one sample for PMMA removal for 18 hours at 23°C in acetone. The surface of the graphene films after PMMA removal was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Helios NanoLab 650, FEI, Hillsboro, OR, USA). SEM images are shown in Figure S1. Clean and crack-free surface is visible for graphene processed with DUV treatment and development in aqueous IPA, while chloroform and acetone treated samples demonstrate slightly lesser surface quality.

Figure S1. SEM images of graphene films after PMMA removal. (a), (d) PMMA removed by DUV treatment and development in aqueous IPA. (b), (e) PMMA removed by 18 hours in acetone. (c), (f) PMMA removed by 18 hours in chloroform

The atomic force microscope (AFM) was also used to study the surface of the graphene films after PMMA removal. The conductive microscopy was by using a Dimension 3100 Bruker scanning probe system equipped with TUNA module under ambient conditions. Measurements

involved PtIr cantilever, 300um length and 0.8N/m spring constant type RMN-12PT300B.

Figure S2 show the AFM results for different samples.

Figure S2. AFM topography of graphene sample with PMMA removed in IPA/water after DUV exposure (top line) and in chloroform (bottom line). It is worth to note that the surface roughness of the graphene prepared by different methods was found to be very similar ($RMS \leq 0.3$ nm).

Detailed results of graphene electrical characterization

For contactless characterization we employed the terahertz time-domain spectroscopy (THz TDS), which has been adapted for such applications¹⁻³. Results THz-TDS transmission measurements were analyzed considering a graphene on the substrate as delta-thin conductive layer, which is described by Drude conductivity model, with fitting parameters of sheet conductivity, scattering time and substrate thickness⁴. Though, remote THz characterization is a powerful tool, but it doesn't provide information on the type of free carriers that are interacting with THz radiation. To get more insight into this, we have provided Ag epoxy contacts to our prepared graphene samples and performed Hall measurements to determine the main carrier type. Results of characterization for all the samples are summarized in Table T1.

Table T1. Electrical parameters of graphene samples extracted from THz-TDS results.

PMMA removal	Processing run	Carrier type from Hall measurements	Sheet resistance R_s ($\Omega/\text{sq.}$)	Sheet carrier density N_s ($\times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	Carrier mobility μ ($\text{cm}^2/(\text{V}\cdot\text{s})$)
DUV1		<i>p</i>	670	2.5	3720
DUV2	Processing run 1	<i>p</i>	840	2.0	3650
Chloroform		<i>n</i>	1100	1.3	4290
DUV3		<i>n</i>	1110	0.8	6910
Chloroform	Processing run 2	<i>n</i>	850	1.3	5890
Acetone		<i>p</i>	850	3.1	2410

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